

Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine research mapping around the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely a VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Analysis techniques data includes: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the DPR ratio; (2) mapping the results of VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the DPR ratio based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the DPR ratio using a Library Research study. The research results show that: (1) based on mapping the distribution of journal publications, there are 610 journal publications around the DPR ratio; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the DPR ratio are divided into 5 clusters and 209 topic items; (3) based on mapping Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 26 topics regarding the influence of the DPR ratio and 62 topics regarding the determinants of the DPR ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the DPR ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) is also an important tool in evaluating company performance in the banking sector. Banks are financial institutions that have unique characteristics in terms of risk and financial management. DPR in the banking sector is used to ensure that banks have sufficient capital to manage risks and maintain long-term financial stability, while meeting shareholder expectations regarding returns on their investments (Ariesa, 2022).

In the banking sector, the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) is a ratio that measures the percentage of a bank's net profit paid to shareholders as dividends. In this case, DPR is an important measure of a bank's ability to generate profits and allocate them efficiently. A bank that has a high DPR shows that the bank can generate sufficient income and has a good policy in paying dividends to shareholders (Budiman, 2022). However, DPR on banking can vary depending on the policies and financial situation of each bank. Banks that are in a stable and growing condition tend to have a higher DPR because these banks have a policy of paying good dividends to shareholders. On the other hand, banks that are in a difficult and uncertain situation, such as in bad economic conditions or in a state of financial crisis, tend to reduce DPR to save capital and allocate more money to reserves. Apart from that, DPR in banking can also be influenced by government regulations and policies related to the banking sector (Anisah, 2022). For example, some regulators may limit the amount of dividends that banks can pay in a given year to ensure the stability of the banking sector as a whole. For example, regulators may require banks to

increase capital reserves at the same time as limiting the amount of dividends that can be paid to shareholders. Overall, DPR remains an important tool for banks to evaluate their financial performance and decide on appropriate dividend payment policies to shareholders. DPR on banking will continue to develop along with developments in the banking sector and financial regulations that continue to change. Therefore, it is important for companies to monitor their DPR regularly and take appropriate actions to ensure financial stability and shareholder satisfaction in the long term (Amelia, 2023).

Several recent studies have discussed DPR in banking. First, research that examines the influence of DPR on bank profitability in Malaysia. The research results show that DPR has a positive influence on bank profitability, which shows that a good dividend payment policy can improve bank financial performance (Yesyurun, 2021). Second, other research which explores the influence of DPR on bank credit risk in Pakistan. The research results show that DPR has a positive influence on bank credit risk, which shows that a dividend payment policy that is too aggressive can reduce the bank's ability to manage credit risk (Suherman, 2021). Third, several studies have paid attention to other influencing factors DPR in banking, such as financial performance, company size, leverage, and external factors such as economic conditions and government regulations, which shows that DPR in banking in ASEAN countries is influenced by financial performance, company size, and external factors such as economic growth and the level of inflation (Syarif, 2020). Overall, research on DPR in banking continues to develop and provides a better understanding of the relationship between DPR and bank financial performance. Apart from that, this research also provides a more comprehensive view of the factors that influence DPR in banking. This can help bank management make the right decisions about dividend payment policies and ensure long-term financial stability.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding DPR in Islamic and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publication of a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) Mapping Research Topics using Library Research to analyze, identify and review articles from Sinta accredited national journal. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the DPR. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research the DPR. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can identify research gaps, and can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) is a ratio that measures the percentage of a company's net profit distributed to shareholders as dividends. DPR in banking refers to the percentage of net profit distributed as dividends to banking shareholders. DPR in banking can vary depending on the dividend policy set by the bank. In some cases, banks may decide to retain most of their net profits for internal purposes, such as to finance company growth or to strengthen capital reserves (Pratiwi, 2021). However, on the other hand, banks can also choose to pay high dividends to demonstrate financial strength and provide attractive income for shareholders. In calculating DPR in banking, the amount of dividends paid by the bank is divided by its net profit. For example, if a bank pays dividends of \$10 million in a certain year, while its net profit is \$50 million in the same year, then the DPR is 20% ($=\$10 \text{ million dividend divided by } \$50 \text{ million net profit}$) (Taufiq, 2015).

Bibliometric studies are studies that use quantitative methods to analyze and evaluate scientific works documented in bibliographic databases. Bibliometric studies involve the measurement and analysis of parameters related to scientific publications, such as publication frequency, authors, subjects, citations, journal or publisher, etc. The aim of bibliometric studies is to provide an understanding of trends and patterns in the development of scientific publications, identify the most influential scientific works, and show the relationship between scientific publications and the advancement of knowledge in a field (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is bibliometric analysis software used to visualize data originating from bibliographic databases. This software can be used to analyze various types of bibliometric data, such as citations, keywords, or subjects. VOSviewer has features that allow users to create visualization maps from bibliometric data, such as network maps map), cluster map, and density map. Network maps can be used to show relationships between scientific works, while cluster maps can be used to show groups of similar scientific works in a particular field. Density maps can be used to show the geographic or thematic distribution of scientific work (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a research method carried out by reviewing literature from various sources related to the research topic being studied. A Library Research study aims to identify, review, and analyze previous literature or literature studies that are relevant to the research topic. In a Library Research study, researchers search for, read, and analyze scientific publications, journals, books, reports, and other documents related to the research topic. After that, the researcher extracted important information from each publication and carried out a synthesis or analysis of the findings found (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Mapping Research Topics using Library Research. The research object is the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR). The data type used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about DPR on Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and the Perish/Harzing software. Tool Data analysis using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Dividend Payout Ratio " and "DPR" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the DPR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around the DPR using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the DPR using a Library Research study (Budianto, 2023a).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications around Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 610 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2002 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about the DPR by year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2002	2	2012	16	2018	64
2007	3	2013	33	2019	60
2008	2	2014	43	2020	80
2009	1	2015	47	2021	78
2010	1	2016	53	2022	56
2011	7	2017	57	2023	7

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Article search results in Perish/Harzing software are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps around the DPR.

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

the VOSViewer software visualization regarding the research development map regarding the DPR ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, there are 5 clusters and 209 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 76 topic items, namely: analysis method, annual report, attention, banking company, capital market structure, cash flow, company value, criteria, data analysis method technique, determinant, dividend distribution payment, policy yield, effect, evidence, financial statement, firm, fluctuation, form, free cash flow, future, hypothesis testing, impact, income, independent variable, index, Indonesian stock exchange, inflation, influence, information, institutional ownership, interest, investment opportunity, investor, Jakarta Islamic index, management, market value, multiple linear regression, non financial company, observation, operating cash flow, ownership structure, panel data regression, path analysis, payout ratio, policy, problem, profit, quantitative approach, regression, relationship, research method sample, secondary data, shareholder, significant effect, influence, negative effect, stock exchange price, test result, time type, value, variable.

- Cluster 2, consists of 41 topic items, namely: assets, beverage company, book value, Indonesian stock exchange, current ratio, panel data, debt, der, dividend payout ratio, dpr, earnings per share, Indonesian securities, eps, equity ratio, financial ratio, food, stock price, criteria, pbv, influence of dividend payout ratio, influence of return, per, company, price book value, price earnings ratio, purposive sampling, ratio, return, roa roe, shares, significant positive effect, significant on dividends, stock returns, analysis techniques, tests, variables.
- Cluster 3, consists of 39 topic items, namely: addition, amount, analysis technique, autocorrelation test, cash ratio, classic assumption test, coefficient, determination, dividend payout ratio, f test, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis test, icmd, Indonesian capital market, Indonesian stock exchange, insider ownership, investment opportunity, ios, level, manufacturing company, multiple regression, normality test, influence of debt, positive influence, r square, regression model, research model, research period, researcher, rest, sample company, sampling technique, significance level, t test, variable debt, variation.
- Cluster 4, consists of 28 topic items, namely: analytical method, company size, financial leverage, firm size, firm value, income smoothing managerial ownership, leverage, liquidity, liquidity, managerial ownership, manufacturing company, multiple regression analysis, influence of profitability, population, profitability, purposive sampling method, sales growth, significant impact, size, square, total assets, company size.
- Cluster 5, consists of 25 topic items, namely: asset growth, asset ratio, bei, cash position, data analysis, empirical evidence, financial report, growth opportunity, idx, Indonesian stock exchange, multiple linear regression, negative on dividends, negative effect, net profit margin, npm, positive effect, property, purposive sampling technique, quantitative research, sample selection, spss version, data analysis techniques, total sample, variable return.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) on Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 26 influences of DPR on Islamic and Conventional Banking (Budianto, 2023b) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023), namely:

(1) Discretionary accruals. The higher the DPR, the smaller the remaining profit that can be allocated to investment or acquisition of new assets. Therefore, companies tend to carry out discretionary accruals to increase their net income. However, in the banking sector, regulators usually limit discretionary accruals. Therefore, the influence of DPR on discretionary accruals in banking may be limited.

(2) Sharia stock beta. If a company increases its DPR, it can reduce the company's ability to make investments or obtain new financing needed to increase the company's growth and stability. This can increase systematic risk and therefore increase the stock's beta. However, the relationship between DPR and sharia stock beta may vary depending on other factors such as company size, ownership structure, and market environment.

(3) Debt to Equity Ratio /DER. If the company chooses to pay high dividends, then the company does not have sufficient funds to obtain new

financing from debt. Therefore, DER may decrease when DPR increases. However, banks can be more flexible in debt management because they have various funding sources such as loans from the central bank or third party funds.

(4) Earning Response Coefficient /ERC. When DPR increases, the company has a tendency to reduce investment or growth, and increase dividend payments to shareholders. This can

affects earnings per share and ERC. Research also shows that a high DPR can reduce ERC because investors assume that high dividends indicate a lack of company investment opportunities. Conversely, a low DPR can increase ERC because investors consider the company to have better investment opportunities in the future.

(5) Earnings Management. When the DPR is low, the company has a tendency to carry out earnings management to increase profits and meet investor expectations. However, when the DPR is high, companies tend not to carry out earnings management because they have enough funds to pay dividends without having to manipulate financial reports.

(6) Holding Period of ordinary shares. When a company pays high dividends, investors looking for stable income and high dividends tend to hold the stock for a longer period of time. This can increase the Holding Period of ordinary shares in the company. However, if a company pays a low dividend, then investors looking for growth tend to buy the stock and sell it in a shorter period of time. This can reduce the Holding Period of ordinary shares in the company.

(7) Debt policy. When DPR is low, banking companies may choose to use available profits to finance investment and growth projects, or pay down debt. Conversely, when DPR is high, banking companies may choose to pay larger dividends and use less profits to pay down debt or finance growth. In this case, a high DPR can influence debt policy by reducing the company's debt ratio.

(8) Company performance. When DPR is low, banking companies can utilize available profits to finance investment and growth, which can increase future revenues and profits. However, if the DPR is too high, banking companies may miss the opportunity to invest their profits to strengthen their position in the market. In this case, the optimal DPR must be found to maximize company performance.

(9) Accounting Conservatism. A high DPR can increase accounting conservatism, meaning companies tend to report lower revenues and profits. This is because companies prefer to maintain sufficient reserve funds to pay future dividends rather than take the risk of reporting higher revenues and profits. Conversely, a low DPR can increase accounting aggressiveness, which means companies tend to report higher revenues and profits to meet investor expectations.

(10) Profit management. When DPR is high, banking management may choose to manipulate financial reports to show better performance, thereby justifying larger dividend payments. Conversely, when DPR is low, banking management may tend to be more conservative in reporting profits to maintain sufficient reserve funds to finance future investment and growth.

(11) Net Profit Margin / NPM. When DPR is high, NPM can decrease because banking companies focus more on paying dividends rather than maintaining profits within the company. However, if DPR is too low, NPM may increase as the company focuses more on investment and future growth.

(12) The value of the company. When DPR is high, investors may find the company less attractive due to lower returns. Conversely, when the DPR is low, investors may find the company more attractive due to higher returns. However, it should be noted that company value is also influenced by other factors such as operational performance and future growth prospects.

(13) Income smoothing. When DPR is high, banking management may tend to smooth out profit fluctuations by shifting profits to reserves or slowing down revenue recognition. This can help ensure stable dividend payments and increase investor confidence. In contrast, when DPR is low, banking management may be more inclined to exhibit greater profit fluctuations to maintain sufficient reserve funds to finance future investments and growth.

(14) Revenue growth. When DPR is high, banking firms may be more inclined to finance development through debt, which could limit future earnings growth. In contrast, when DPR is low, banking firms may be more inclined to use internal profits to finance growth, which may increase the firm's ability to grow.

(15) Pecking Orders. When DPR is high, banking companies may be more inclined to use debt and other external funds rather than internal funding or new shares to finance investment and growth. In contrast, when DPR is low, banking firms may be more inclined to use internal profits or issue new shares to finance investment and growth.

(16) Use of debt. When the DPR is low, banking companies may be more inclined to use debt as a source of funding because using debt can help the company save cash which will be used to pay dividends. However, when the DPR is high, banking companies may be more inclined to reduce their use of debt because they have used a large portion of their profits to pay dividends to shareholders.

(17) Valuation of company equity. When the DPR is high, investments in banking companies can become more attractive to investors seeking steady income, and this can increase demand and valuation of the company's equity. Conversely, if the DPR is low, the banking company may be unattractive to investors seeking dividend income, and the company's equity valuation may be negatively affected.

(18) Price to Earnings Ratio /PER. When DPR is high, PER can increase because investors tend to assess companies with high DPR as stable and reliable companies. However, if the DPR is low, the PER may be lower

because investors may not view the company as stable and reliable.

(19) Price to Book Value / PBV. When DPR is high, banking companies may have lower book values because most of the profits have been paid out as dividends, and this can reduce PBV. Conversely, if the DPR is low, banking companies may have a higher book value, and PBV may increase.

(20) Profit prediction. When DPR is low, banking companies may have more cash available to reinvest into the business, which can increase future profits. However, if the DPR is high, the banking company may have less cash available for investment and this may reduce future profit predictions.

(21) returns. When DPR is high, banking companies may have lower stock returns because most of the profits have been paid out as dividends, and this may reduce profits reinvested into the business and future company performance. However, if the DPR is low, banking companies may have higher stock returns because more profits are reinvested into the business to improve future company performance. Systematic risk. When DPR is high, systematic risk in banking companies may increase because investors may view the banking company as a stable company with stable profits, which can make banking company shares less responsive to market changes. However, if the DPR is low, systematic risk on banking companies may decrease because investors may have more confidence in banking companies retaining profits to reinvest into the business, which may make banking company shares more responsive to market changes.

(22) Capital structure. When the DPR is high, banking companies may have less debt, because most of the profits have been paid out as dividends. Conversely, if the DPR is low, a banking company may have more debt because less profits are paid out as dividends and more profits are reinvested into the business. This can affect the capital structure of banking companies and can influence the company's future risk and performance.

(23) Company size. When DPR is high, banking firms may be smaller in terms of assets because most of the profits have been paid out as dividends. Conversely, if the DPR is low, the banking firm may be larger in terms of assets because more profits are reinvested into the business. This may affect the company's ability to grow the business and expand market share in the future.

(24) Value Added Intellectual Coefficient/VAIC. When the DPR is high, banking companies may be less interested in developing intellectual value because most of the profits have been paid out as dividends. Conversely, if DPR is low, banking firms may be more inclined to develop intellectual value because more profits can be invested into development

HR, information systems, and knowledge management. Therefore, DPR can influence VAIC in banking companies.

(25) Stock price volatility. When the DPR is high, banking company stock prices may be less stable because investors may view the banking company as a stable company with stable profits, which may make banking company shares less responsive to market changes. Conversely, if the DPR is low, banking company stock prices may be more stable because investors may have more confidence in banking companies retaining profits to reinvest into the business, which may make banking company shares more responsive to market changes.

(26) Stock trading volume. When the DPR is high, the trading volume of banking company shares may be lower because investors may be less interested in buying or selling the banking company's shares. Conversely, if the DPR is low, the trading volume of banking company shares may be higher because investors may be more interested in buying or selling shares of the banking company because they believe that the banking company has higher growth potential.

Mapping the Library Research Study regarding the Determinant Variables of Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 62 determinant variables for DPR in Islamic and Conventional Banking (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Emiliani et al., 2023), namely:

(1) Free cash flow. The greater the free cash flow, the more likely the bank will pay dividends. This is because banks have more funds that can be used to meet their cash needs, including paying dividends to shareholders. Therefore, the greater the free cash flow, the more likely the DPR will increase.

(2) Operating cash flow. The greater the operating cash flow, the more likely the company will pay dividends. However, depending on working capital and investment requirements, a company may have to use a portion of its operating cash flow to meet its operational needs. Therefore, the influence of operating cash flow on banking DPR may vary.

(3) Agency Cost / agency fee. Agency costs can reduce DPR by limiting a company's ability to pay dividends because management may prefer to use the money for their personal interests or projects that do not benefit shareholders.

(4) Asset Growth. If banks experience rapid growth, then they will likely choose to hold cash for future investments and increase future shareholder returns. This may reduce the DPR at this time. However, if asset growth is relatively slow,

then it is likely that banks will be more inclined to increase the DPR at this time.

(5) Basic Earning Power /BEP. BEP measures a company's ability to generate profits before interest and tax charges on its total assets. The higher the BEP, the more likely the company will pay higher dividends because the company has a greater ability to generate profits. Thus, the higher the BEP of a bank, the more likely it is that its DPR will be high.

(6) Bird in the hand /BIT. BIT refers to certain profits compared to expected profits in the future. The greater the guaranteed profit a company has, the more likely it is that the company will pay higher dividends because the company has the ability to pay dividends with its current profits. So the higher the BIT, the higher the probability of a high DPR.

(7) Board of Commissioners /BOC. The BOC is responsible for overseeing company management and ensuring that the company operates effectively and efficiently. If the BOC has a policy that supports high dividend payments, then banking DPR will most likely also be high. However, if the BOC does not support high dividend payments, the DPR will likely be lower.

(8) Board Governance. Board Governance refers to the way a company is governed and run by a board of directors. If the company has good and transparent governance, the DPR tends to be higher because investors feel trust and confidence in the company. On the other hand, if corporate governance is poor, the DPR will likely be lower because investors will be hesitant to obtain dividends from the company.

(9) Capital Expenditure /CAPEX. If a company spends a lot of funds on CAPEX, then it is likely that its DPR will be lower because the company has to retain income to generate investment. Conversely, if CAPEX is low, DPR will likely be higher because the company has more cash available to distribute to shareholders.

(10) Cash Position / cash position. If a company has a large cash position, it is likely that its DPR will be higher because the company has more cash available to distribute to shareholders. However, if the cash position is low, the DPR will likely be lower because the company must retain income for operational needs.

(11) Cash Ratio. The higher the cash ratio, the more likely the company will pay higher dividends because the company has the ability to pay short-term debt with available cash. Conversely, if the cash ratio is low, the DPR will likely be lower because the company must retain income to pay short-term debt.

(12) Current Ratio /CR. The higher the CR, the greater the possibility that the company will pay higher dividends because the company has the ability to pay short-term debt using its current assets

owned. However, if the CR is low, the DPR will likely be lower because the company must retain earnings to pay short-term debt.

(13) Collateralizable Assets /COL. The greater the COL of a banking company, the more likely the company is to borrow money and use these funds to pay higher dividends to shareholders. However, if the COL is low, the DPR will likely be lower because the company must retain earnings to obtain the necessary collateral.

(14) Debt to Equity Ratio /DER. The higher the DER, the greater the company's financial risk and the possibility that its DPR will be lower because the company will have to pay higher interest on its debt and also withhold earnings to pay off that debt. Conversely, if the DER is low, the DPR will likely be higher because the company has more money available to distribute to shareholders.

(15) Debt to Total Assets /DTA. The higher the DTA, the greater the company's financial risk and the lower the DPR will likely be because the company will have to pay higher interest on its debt and withhold earnings to repay that debt. Conversely, if DTA is low, DPR will likely be higher because the company has more money available to distribute to shareholders.

(16) Dividend Payout Ratio /DPR. The higher the DPR, the more money the company pays out as dividends. However, a DPR that is too high can reduce a company's ability to reinvest profits for future growth, thereby reducing long-term profits. Therefore, the DPR must be determined carefully and must be balanced with the company's investment needs.

(17) Earnings Per Share /EPS. The higher the EPS, the more profit the company generates to share with shareholders. If EPS is high and DPR is low, the company can use profits to strengthen its financial position and develop its business. However, if EPS is low and DPR is high, the company may lose the ability to grow its business due to lack of funds.

(18) Financial Leverage. The greater the use of debt, the higher the Financial Leverage. If the company has high financial leverage, the DPR must be determined carefully to minimize the risk of bankruptcy. If the DPR is too high, the company may lose the ability to pay its debts and experience financial problems. Conversely, if the DPR is low, the company can use profits to pay debts and reduce the risk of bankruptcy.

(19) Free Cash Flow / FCF. The influence of FCF on the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in banking can be said to be positive. FCF is the cash flow available after capital expenditures and operational costs are met. The greater the FCF generated by a banking company, the greater the company's ability to pay dividends to shareholders. Therefore, the greater the FCF of a banking company, the greater the possibility of a higher DPR as well.

(20) Good Corporate Governance /GCG. GCG has a positive influence on DPR in banking. GCG is a set of best practices in managing a company which aims to increase company value and protect the interests of stakeholders. In the banking context, GCG can increase public trust in banking and strengthen the company's image. Thus, banking companies that implement GCG well tend to distribute larger dividends.

(21) Growth Potential / growth potential. The influence of Growth Potential on the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in banking can be said to be positive. The high growth potential of banking companies shows that the company has a great opportunity to earn greater profits in the future. This will allow the company to pay higher dividends to shareholders. However, companies may also choose to retain some profits for future investment, thereby influencing the DPR.

(22) Growth Opportunities /GO. In the banking industry, GO can influence DPR because banking is a business that relies heavily on investment in growth opportunities. Banks need to invest a large part of their income to develop business and increase capital. Therefore, the higher the growth opportunity, the higher the investment required, and the lower the DPR. However, GO's influence on the DPR is not always negative. If banks have good growth opportunities, they can increase their revenues and in turn increase net profits. In this case, banks can pay higher dividends and still maintain the investment necessary for growth.

(23) Idiosyncratic Risk. Idiosyncratic Risk or company-specific risk can influence DPR in banking. Company-specific risks may occur due to poor management policies or other internal problems. If the company's specific risk is high, then the company will tend to choose to retain some profits rather than pay higher dividends. Therefore, firm-specific risks can lower DPR.

(24) Institutional Ownership. Institutional ownership can also influence DPR on banking. Institutional ownership can increase investor confidence in the company and improve the company's image in the eyes of investors. Thus, banking companies with high institutional ownership tend to distribute larger dividends to gain investor trust and satisfaction.

(25) Investment Opportunity Set /IOS. Investment opportunities can influence DPR in banking. If a banking company has a high IOS, the company will tend to retain some of its profits to invest in more profitable investment opportunities. However, if IOS is low, the company will tend to pay higher dividends.

(26) Inflation. Inflation has a complex influence on DPR in banking. If inflation is high, the operational costs of banking companies can increase, which can affect the company's ability to pay

dividend. However, at the same time, moderate inflation can increase banking company revenues because interest rates tend to rise. If banking companies succeed in taking advantage of these conditions, the DPR can increase.

(27) Interdependence. Interdependence or dependence between companies can also influence DPR in banking. If there is dependence between companies, banking companies will tend to be more careful in making decisions regarding dividend payments. This is because banking companies need to consider the effect of dividend payments on relationships with other companies. Therefore, interdependence can influence the DPR.

(28) Innovation. Innovation can also influence DPR on banking. Innovation can help banking companies to increase efficiency and generate greater profits. However, if innovation requires large investments, then banking companies may choose to retain some profits rather than pay higher dividends.

(29) Independent Commissioners. Independent Commissioners or independent commissioners have an important role in maintaining Good Corporate Governance (GCG) in companies, including banking companies. By having independent commissioners who have extensive experience and knowledge, banking companies can ensure that decisions regarding the DPR are based on rational and fair considerations. Therefore, the existence of independent commissioners can strengthen investor confidence in banking companies and increase DPR.

(30) Debt policy. Debt policy can also influence DPR on banking. If a banking company has a strict debt policy, the company will tend to allocate more cash to pay debt than to pay dividends. However, if a banking company has a flexible debt policy, the company can have more cash to pay dividends.

(31) Managerial ownership. Managerial ownership refers to share ownership by managers or leaders company. Managerial ownership can motivate managers to maximize company profits and increase share value. This can have a positive impact on DPR as managers will seek to increase cash flow and ensure consistent dividend payments.

(32) Public ownership. Public ownership refers to share ownership by investors who are not related to company management. Public ownership can influence DPR because investors can demand higher dividend payments. If banking companies want to maintain investor support, they should consider paying fairly high dividends.

(33) Insider ownership. Insider ownership or insider ownership refers to ownership of shares by the individual or group that owns it access to internal company information, such as company managers or owners.

Insider ownership can motivate company managers or owners to maintain good company performance and increase share value, which can have a positive impact on DPR.

(34) Employee welfare. Employee welfare can also influence DPR in banking companies. If banking companies provide competitive salaries and benefits and pay attention to employee welfare, employees will be more motivated to work hard and produce better performance, which ultimately can increase DPR.

(35) Net profit. If a banking company generates large enough profits, the company can allocate part of these profits to pay dividends. On the other hand, if a banking company experiences losses or low profits, the company must prioritize using it to improve performance and financial stability.

(36) Liquidity. If a banking company has high enough liquidity, the company can allocate part of its cash to pay dividends. However, if a banking company experiences liquidity problems, the company must prioritize using its cash to settle obligations and develop the business.

(37) Leverage Ratio. The higher the leverage ratio, the greater the company's risk of bankruptcy, so the company tends to retain more cash to strengthen its financial position, which can reduce the DPR.

(38) Market to Book Value /MBV. The higher the MBV, the higher the company's market valuation, which can increase the DPR because the company can use its shares as currency to pay dividends.

(39) Net Profit Margin / NPM. The higher the NPM, the greater the company's profits, which can increase the DPR.

(40) Exchange rate. If the local currency weakens, banking firms may feel pressure to increase DPR to offset rising import costs and help protect the value of shareholder wealth from inflation. Conversely, if the local currency strengthens, the company may consider lowering the DPR to invest more funds into the business.

(41) Past Dividends. Dividend payment history can influence future dividend payment policies. If a company has paid stable and consistent dividends in the past, then its future dividend payment policy is likely to be more stable. Conversely, if a company has never paid dividends or cut dividend payments significantly in the past, then the company may be inclined not to pay dividends or pay less dividends.

(42) Asset growth. Stable and consistent asset growth can provide strong financial support for banking companies. This can allow the company to pay dividends consistently and increase DPR along with continued growth. However, if the company's asset growth is unstable or decreasing, then the company may need to consider holding back dividend payments or reducing the DPR.

(43) Company growth. The company's overall growth can influence its dividend payment policy. If a company experiences rapid growth and requires resources to invest in further growth, then the company may withhold dividend payments or reduce the DPR. On the other hand, if the company experiences slow or stable growth, then the company may maintain or increase its DPR.

(44) Dividend tax changes. Changes in dividend tax rules can affect dividend payment policies in banking companies. If dividend tax rules change so that companies have to pay higher taxes on dividend payments, then companies may withhold dividend payments or lower the DPR to avoid higher taxes. On the other hand, if the dividend tax rules change so that the company can save tax, then the company may increase the DPR.

(45) Quick Ratio. Quick Ratio is a financial ratio that measures a company's ability to pay its short-term obligations with current assets that can be immediately converted into cash. The higher the Quick Ratio, the greater the company's ability to pay dividends consistently. This is because a high Quick Ratio indicates that the company has sufficient liquidity to pay its short-term obligations and has sufficient resources to pay dividends.

(46) Price-to-Earnings Ratio (PER). PER can influence dividend payment policies in banking companies. Companies that have a higher market ratio tend to be more liked by investors and have the potential to pay larger dividends. Conversely, companies that have a lower market ratio may need to withhold dividend payments or lower the DPR because investors are not investing in these companies with a high level of confidence.

(47) Profitability ratio. Profitability ratios, such as Return on Investment (ROI), can influence dividend payment policies in banking companies. Companies that have a high profitability ratio tend to have a larger dividend payment policy because they have greater income. On the other hand, companies that have a low profitability ratio may need to withhold dividend payments or reduce the DPR because the profits generated are not sufficient to pay dividends consistently.

(48) Return On Assets / ROA. ROA measures the company's effectiveness in generating profits from each asset owned. The higher the ROA, the more likely the company will pay larger dividends because it has the ability to generate profits from the assets it owns.

(49) Return On Equity /ROE. ROE measures how much profit a company generates compared to its equity. The higher the ROE, the more likely the company will pay larger dividends because it has the ability to generate high profits for shareholders.

(50) Auditor's reputation. A good auditor's reputation can increase investor confidence and make the company more liquid to pay dividends. This is because a trusted auditor can guarantee that the financial reports issued by the company are truly accurate.

(51) Business risk. Banking companies must pay attention to business risks associated with dividend payment policies. If the company faces high business risks, then the DPR may need to be reduced to avoid bankruptcy or inability to pay debts. Conversely, if business risk is low, the company may consider paying larger dividends.

(52) R&D Investments. If a bank invests in research and development (R&D) to improve operational efficiency, customer experience, or develop new products and services that can increase the bank's revenue, then its DPR may be affected. If R&D investments have a positive impact on bank revenues and profits, then the bank may choose to increase the DPR by distributing more dividends to shareholders.

(53) Sales Growth. If the bank succeeds in increasing sales and earnings, its DPR may be affected. This is because the bank will have more profits to distribute as dividends to shareholders. However, banks may also choose to use additional profits to make larger investments or pay down debt.

(54) Share ownership structure. The shareholding structure can influence the DPR because banks may pay more attention to the interests of majority shareholders than minority shareholders. If the majority of shareholders want the DPR to be low, then the bank may distribute less dividends. On the other hand, if the majority of shareholders want the DPR to be high, then the bank may distribute more dividends.

(55) Ultimate ownership structure. The ultimate ownership structure refers to the share ownership that exists behind the registered shareholders. If a bank's ultimate ownership structure indicates strong influence from institutional investors or large financial groups, then its DPR may be lower. This is because such investors tend to be more interested in long-term growth than dividend payments.

(56) Capital structure. Capital structure can influence DPR in banking because changes in the debt-to-equity ratio can affect the bank's ability to distribute dividends. If banks have high debt, then they may need to use profits to pay interest on debt and maintain capital requirements required by regulators. This can affect the bank's ability to pay high dividends. However, if banks have a healthy capital structure and do not rely too much on debt, then they may find it easier to distribute larger dividends.

(57) Independent commissioner structure. The presence of independent commissioners in the banking management structure can influence the DPR. Independent commissioner

is usually responsible for ensuring that bank management conducts business with a high degree of ethics and transparency and takes into account the interests of all stakeholders, including shareholders. If a bank has a strong and transparent management structure, its DPR may be higher because shareholders feel more confident and comfortable with the bank's management.

(58) Tax Rate. Tax rates can influence the DPR on banking because taxes are expenses that banks must pay from their profits before distributing them as dividends. If tax rates are low, then banks may have more profits to distribute as dividends to shareholders. However, if the tax rate is high, then the bank may choose to use additional profits to pay taxes or make larger investments.

(59) Time Discounting. Time discounting can influence DPR in banking because banks must take into account the time value of money in making decisions about dividend distribution. If banks consider that the time value of money is very important, then they may choose not to pay dividends and use profits to invest more capital to earn greater returns in the future. However, if the bank considers that dividend payments are important to maintain good relations with shareholders and maintain a stable share price, then its DPR may be higher.

(60) Total Assets Turnover /TATO. TATO measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate sales. The higher the TATO of a company, the more efficiently the company's assets are used to generate income. An increase in TATO can increase a company's ability to pay dividends due to the increase in income generated, and vice versa.

(61) Tangibility. Tangibility refers to the number of physical assets owned by a company. The higher the level of tangibility of a company, the easier these assets can be sold or used as collateral, so that the company can easily obtain additional funding. This can affect DPR in banking because if companies have a lot of physical assets and are easy to sell, they may be more confident in paying higher dividends.

(62) Company size. Company size can influence DPR in banking because larger companies tend to have more resources and access to greater funding sources. Larger companies also tend to be more financially stable and have a larger customer base. All of these factors can affect a company's ability to pay higher dividends.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking over a period of time from 2002 to 2023 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta,

there are 610 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results regarding the DPR ratio in Sharia Banking and Conventionally divided into 5 clusters and 209 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 76 topics, cluster 2 consists of 41 topics, cluster 3 consists of 39 topics, cluster 4 consists of 28 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 25 topics. Third, based on the mapping of the Library Research study, there are 26 topics related to the influence of the DPR ratio on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: discretionary accruals, sharia share beta, Debt to Equity Ratio / DER, Earning Response Coefficient / ERC, Earning Management, Holding Period common shares, debt policy, company performance, conservatism, earnings management, Net Profit Margin / NPM, company value, income smoothing, income growth, pecking order, use of debt, company equity assessment, Price to Earnings Ratio / PER, Price to Book Value / PBV, profit predictions, stock returns, capital structure, company size, Value Added Intellectual Coefficient / VAIC, stock price volatility, and stock trading volume.

Furthermore, there are 62 topics related to the determinants of the DPR ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: free cash flow, operating cash flow, Agency Cost / agency costs, Asset Growth, Basic Earning Power / BEP, Bird in the hand / BIT, Board of Commissioners /BOC, Board Governance, Capital Expenditure /CAPEX, Cash Position /cash position, Cash Ratio, Current Ratio /CR, Collateralizable Assets /COL, Debt to Equity Ratio /DER, Debt to Total Assets /DTA, Dividend Payout Ratio / DPR, Earning Per Share /EPS, Financial Leverage, Free Cash Flow /FCF, Good Corporate Governance /GCG, Growth Potential /growth potential, Growth Opportunity /GO, Idiosyncratic Risk, Institutional Ownership, Investment Opportunity Set /IOS, inflation, interdependence, innovation, Independent Commissioners, debt policy, managerial ownership, public ownership, insider ownership, employee welfare, net profit, liquidity, Leverage Ratio, Market to Book Value /MBV, Net Profit Margin /NPM, exchange rate, past dividend, asset growth, company growth, changes in dividend tax, quick ratio, Price-to-Earnings Ratio (PER), profitability ratio, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, auditor reputation, business risk, R&D Investment, sales growth, share ownership structure, legal ownership structure, capital structure, independent commissioner structure, tax rate, Time Discounting, Total Assets Turnover / TATO, Tangibility, and company size.

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